

THERMAL CYCLE ANALYSIS ON SHINGLED GLASS – GLASS SAMPLES WITH SHJ CELLS

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ABSTRACT:

For years photovoltaic (PV) modules were manufactured with 60 or 72 cells in glass / back sheet designs. Since R&D teams around the world simulated the potential to increase the module efficiency by modifying the designs, the industry develops new production machines to realize those. One such novel approach is the shingling – here the wafer is cut into small stripes. In a module, the stripes are overlapping each other at the ends and an ECA interconnects two cells together. To study the thermal long-term stability, we build mini-modules in various designs with shingled SHJ cells and applied an extended thermal stress sequence (3x IEC) to those samples. We analysed the ageing process with image-based and electrical setups.

Keywords: stability, shingled, heterojunction

1 INTRODUCTION

Since wafer-based solar cells become less expensive it makes sense to cover the pv-module surface full of those and reach high cell-to-module (CTM) [1] values. For that singled approach the wafers have to cut into smaller piece. Typical cut shingled pieces are 1/5 or 1/6. Shingled cells were not soldered – this are connected with an Electrically Conductive Adhesives (ECA) [2]. It has to be conductive and mechanical flexible at the same time. It can be assumed that such a connection is susceptible to thermo-mechanical stresses, therefore we decided to laminate our samples in a symmetric glass-glass design in order to protect the solar cell in the neutral axis from tensile and compressive stresses. [3]

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this paper we studied the thermal stability of shingled single heterojunction samples laminated in glass – glass design. The layout of such a sample is shown in Figure 1 & 2.

Figure 1: Design of the shingled glass – glass SHJ mini modules.

Figure 2: Layout of a shingled glass – glass SHJ mini modules (left: electrical layout; right: realized sample).

Each mini module is configured into two shingle strings independent gathered in one mini module. Per string there are twelve 1/6 cutted shingled SHJ cells in series connected. The samples vary into the cell thickness and the cell geometry (full and pseudo square (PSQ)). A detailed sample overview is displayed in table 1.

Table 1: Sample overview

Cell thickness μm	Module Nb	String name	Type	Batch
120	037 039	Highlite 037BH* Highlite 039AH	Full PSQ	H
120	040 041	Highlite 040A ; Highlite 040B Highlite 041A ; Highlite 041B	Full PSQ	I
120	042 044	Highlite 042A ; Highlite 042B Highlite 044A ; Highlite 044B	Full PSQ	J
120	046 047	Highlite 046A ; Highlite 046B Highlite 047A ; Highlite 047B	Full PSQ	K
120	048 037 039	Highlite 048A ; Highlite 048B ; Highlite 037AL Highlite 039BL	Full Full PSQ	L
120	032	Highlite 032A ; Highlite 032B	Full	F
TOTAL :	10			
Cell thickness μm	Module Nb	String name	Type	Batch
160	013	Highlite 013A ; Highlite 013B	Full	A
160	018	Highlite 018A ; Highlite 018B	Full	B
160	024	Highlite 024A ; Highlite 024B	Full	C
160	028	Highlite 028A ; Highlite 028B	PSQ	D
160	029	Highlite 029A ; Highlite 029B ;	Full	E
160	035 036	Highlite 035A ; Highlite 035B Highlite 036A ; Highlite 036B	Full	G
TOTAL :	7			

In total 17 mini modules were manufactured to which we applied the test sequence shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Applied test sequence.

Initially we carried out IV characterization at STC and electroluminescence (EL) imaging, followed by 6x TC 100 (according to the IEC 61215). After each step of TC 100, intermediate IV characteristics and EL images were taken. The full test sequence ends with the final IV and EL characterization. Upon the EL imaging, due to the strong emitting NIR signal of the SHJ cells, the injected current was set to 0.07x I_{sc}.

3 RESULTS

To have more statistics on that box plots diagrams were plotted for the 120 μm and 160 μm solar cells. Figure 3 shows the box plot diagram of the relative to initial Pmax degradation.

Figure 3: Degradation in Pmax (top) and FF (bottom) of all samples.

Some samples show a strong initial degradation (Ploss >5% after 1x TC100). While I_{sc} and V_{oc} are stable (not shown here), the FF degrades as well. Therefore, it seems those samples have an interconnecting problem. A deeper analysis shows there is a interconnecting problem between the first/last cell in a string and the ribbon. To have more statistics on that box plots diagrams were plotted for the 120 μm and 160 μm solar cells.

Figure 4: Pmax Degradation of the samples with 160 μm.

The Samples (n = 16) with wafer thickness of 160μm showed 6x TC100 an average Ploss relative to initial of -3.2% (-2.4% without the samples with initial degradation).

Figure 5: Pmax Degradation of the samples with 120 μm.

The Samples (n = 16) with a wafer thickness of 120μm showed after 6x TC100 average Ploss relative to initial of -1.5% (without the strong initial degraded samples).

The electroluminescence and electrical data for four samples at different TC stages are presented here.

Figure 6: Electroluminescence images of the different samples at different test levels.

Except sample 39BL no major additional changes to the initial state of the modules are to report. On 39BL an interconnection problem becomes visible.

The relative changes of the electrical data from the same samples are shown next.

Figure 7: Degradation of the electrical data due to temperature cycle stress of the different samples.

Sample 39BL shows the largest degradation, followed by sample 28A. Both samples are PSQ but with different cell thicknesses. Sample 39BL cells are 120 µm thick and sample 28A cells are 160 µm.

4 SUMMARY

We have designed and thermal cycle tested glass - glass mini modules with shingled SHJ solar cells. The main variation of the solar cells was the wafer thickness. Batch 1 had 160µm and batch 2 had 120µm. We applied six cycles of TC-Test (-40°C ... +85°C) without current injection to those. That activity was assisted by initial, intermediate, and final STC and EL analyses.

We noticed at same samples an initial degradation in Pmax and FF. A deeper investigation made sure that at those was an interconnection issue at the first/last cell and the copper ribbon, while the shingled cell to cell connection was properly functioning.

After completing 6x TC100 we noticed that both thicknesses (160µm and 120µm) showed a comparable degradation without taking the samples with the initial degradation into account. In detail the 160µm samples showed an average in Ploss of -2.4% (without the samples with initial degradation) and the 120µm samples showed an average in Ploss of of -1.5% (without the strong initial

degraded samples). At that point it can be summarized that no higher risk on thinner solar cells for application at shingled modules in glass – glass design could be determined. Furthermore, we also observed at samples with PSQ a stronger degradation which isn't fully understood yet.

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6 REFERENCES

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